

New European Bauhaus Academy

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

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Train the Trainer pilot course for professionals in timber construction

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**Circular
Bio-based
Europe**

Joint Undertaking

Co-funded by
the European Union

Pilot Course 'Train the trainer'

Aim

- Strengthen the quality of timber construction education by empowering the people who teach

WHY

- Results of surveys (e.g. "eLABoration Wood") revealed:
 - Deficits in teaching quality
 - Outdated content
 - Lack of practical relevance
- Developed in cooperation with New European Bauhaus Academy + Holzbau Austria + BOKU University + University of Education of Upper Austria

Pilot Course 'Train the trainer'

Goal

- Develop a structured course that combines technical expertise with modern didactics
- Strengthen trainers as multipliers
- Create a European-wide compatible programme that is academically recognised

Pilot Course 'Train the trainer'

Topics covered

- **Bio-based materials**, and the nature-based solutions they represent, as an important aspect of the NEB's approach to improving the sustainability of the built environment.
- **Buildings** - updating existing buildings and designing/constructing modern sustainable buildings according to NEB values.
- **Cultural Heritage** buildings and objects - modern techniques in combination with traditional skills to maintain cultural heritage objects.
- **Design approaches** supporting sustainability goals, circularity, sufficiency, accessibility, and occupant wellbeing.
- Other relevant areas: **Quality management in structural detailing**. Avoiding technical mistakes, increasing reliability, and thus the acceptance of sustainable construction methods.

Pilot Course 'Train the trainer'

Webinar

- Building physics, fire protection, sound insulation, NEB Academy

Flipped Classroom (Participants rotated through several stations)

- Condetti workshop analysing and designing timber construction details
- Dendrochronology and historic roof structures
- Innovations in engineered wood products
- Guided tour of BOKU's research laboratories

Excursions

Rubner Holzbau: prefabrication facilities

B.R.I.O. timber- hybrid housing project in Vienna

Church: baroque roof structure

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Impact

- Sets new standards for teacher education in timber construction
- Strengthens SMEs as better trained teachers produce better trained professionals
- Supports sustainable and circular construction, fully aligned with the goals of the New European Bauhaus initiative
- Becomes compatible across Europe through cooperation with the NEB Academy

Participation Certificate recognized by

- University of Education of Upper Austria
- NEBAP HUB of NEB Academy

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Feedback

- High expertise of the lecturers
- Strong practical relevance
- Clear structure of the programme
- Excellent balance between theory and hands-on learning

Main conclusion

This course should be the beginning of a long-term transformation in how timber construction is taught.

Outlook

- Annual
- National and international recognised programme
- Platform for developing new learning materials
- Strengthening cooperation between schools and industry

Pilot Course 'Train the trainer'

NEBA Recognition Framework

- **Beautiful:** An excursion provides the highest level of sensory experience in relation to the content conveyed.
- **Sustainable:** New timber construction materials, historic roof construction
- **Together:** promotes the status of craftsmen and provides a forum for exchange between craftsmen, technicians, and scientists.

- **Participatory:** Co-creation exercises
- **Multi-level:** local, national, and regional perspectives
- **Transdisciplinary:** co-created by academia, trainers of apprentices, and skilled workers

Pilot Course 'Train the trainer' - videoclip

English:

https://youtu.be/OG_BkwlgVHY

German:

<https://youtu.be/NTYPuMnOJnc>